

A Retrospective Study to Assess the Findings of Ultrasonography in Patients with Ovarian Tumour

Aishwerya Singh¹, Sanjeev Suman², Vijay Shankar Prasad³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor and HOD, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 11-09-2023 / Revised: 20-10-2023 / Accepted: 27-11-2023

Corresponding Author: Dr. Aishwerya Singh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the findings of ultrasonography in patients with ovarian tumour. **Material & Methods:** A retrospective study carried out on 100 patients of ovarian tumours referred to Department of Radio-diagnosis at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India from June 2020 to May 2021. Sociodemographic data, clinical history and clinical examination findings were taken from OBGY department records. Ultrasonography findings were noted. Data analysed with appropriate statistical tests.

Results: In present study, most of the patients (35%) with ovarian tumour were in the age group 51 year old and above, followed by age group of 41-50 years (28%). Mean age of the patient was 45.35 ± 3.4 years. In our study, most common symptom was abdominal pain 94 (94%) followed by abdominal mass 65 (65%). Backache was seen 32 (32%) patients. pressure symptoms were seen in 20 (20%) patients. Pressure symptoms included increased frequency of micturation, retention of urine and GI symptoms like constipation. Majority of the patients 34 (34%) were having cystic + solid consistency followed by cystic consistency 32 (32%). Solid consistency on ultrasonography was seen in 30 (30%). Liver metastasis was seen in 4 (4%) patients. In present study, based on ultrasonography findings most of the benign ovarian tumours were having cystic consistency. Most of the malignant tumour was having both cystic and solid consistency. 4 patients with malignant ovarian tumour had liver metastasis. Association between tumour type and ultrasonography finding was found to be significant ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: On ultrasonography benign ovarian tumours are having cystic consistency and malignant tumours were having cystic+ solid consistency.

Keywords: Benign, Malignant tumors, Ovary, Ultrasonography

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Ovary is a main organ of reproduction but its tumour is always notorious Ovarian cancer is one of the leading cancers in Indian women. Ovarian tumours are complex tumours which are diagnosed very late due to asymptomatic initially. [1] The pathology of ovarian tumour is one of the most complex areas of gynaecology, because the ovaries give rise to greater range and variety of tumours than does any other organ. [2] In India, ovarian cancer is the third leading site of cancer among women after cervix and breast cancer. [3] A female's risk at birth of having ovarian tumour sometime in her life is 6-7%, of having ovarian cancer is almost 1.5% and dying from ovarian cancer is 1%. The age adjusted incidence rates of ovarian cancer vary between 5.4

and 8.0 per 100,000 population in different parts of the country. [4]

Ovarian tumour arises in any age group and can be classified based on cells of their origin into epithelial, sex cord stromal, germ cell and metastatic types. A number of non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesion occur within the ovaries. They can present from the neonatal age to post-menopausal age. Benign ovarian cysts are the commonest constituting about 90% of ovarian tumours. Most commonly observed tumour is epithelial tumors counting about 85% to 90% of all ovarian malignancies. Histologic subtypes in epithelial ovarian cancer include serous, mucinous, endometrioid, clear cell, and undifferentiated tumors. The major risk factor is the

family history. Other associated risk factors are excess body weight, Height, Cigarette smoking and Physical inactivity. [5,6] Ovarian tumours are generally difficult to detect until they are of advanced stage or large in size. Ovarian malignancies are diagnosed late, because of non-specific symptoms initially like discomfort, bloating back pain or urinary symptoms or mainly asymptomatic. [7] Symptoms appear in later stage of malignancy. Most ovarian tumors cannot be distinguished confidently on the basis of their clinical or gross characteristics alone. [8]

Dilemma of differentiating a benign from a malignant tumour always exists by clinical examination. Imaging by USG though helps to locate origin size, consistency of tumour but diagnosis of malignancy in ovarian tumour by USG, CA125, MRI and other method is difficult.¹ Ultrasonography is a relatively simple and non-invasive diagnostic method that provides clinicians with useful information relevant for determining the optimal management strategy for a given patient. Previous studies observed that Ultrasonography can accurately characterize about 90% of adnexal masses and the reported sensitivity and specificity of US for detecting ovarian malignancies is 88%-96% and 90%- 96%, respectively. [9-11] Ultrasound is important for early detection of ovarian tumours and it can be a guide for further management. Hence, Present study was conducted to study the ultrasonographic features of ovarian tumours.

Material & Methods

A retrospective study carried out on 100 patients of ovarian tumours referred to Department of Radiodiagnosis at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India from June 2020 to May 2021. Sociodemographic data, clinical history and clinical examination findings were taken from OBGY department records. Ultrasonography findings were noted. Data analysed with appropriate statistical tests.

Patients having solid ovarian mass and suspected of having ovarian tumour were enrolled in the study. A valid written consent was taken from the patients after explaining study to them.

Inclusion criteria:

1. All patients with solid ovarian mass detected clinically
2. All patients with cystic ovarian lesions more than 6 cms.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Ovarian cyst less than 6 cms with clear cysts
2. Patients not willing to participate in the study

Methodology

All the patients admitted in the obstetrics and gynaecology department with ovarian tumour and referred to radiology department were studied. Data collected with pretested questionnaire. Data regarding sociodemographic data, clinical history and clinical examination were taken from records of OBGY department. All patients underwent ultrasonography of abdomen and pelvis. Ultrasound findings of the ovarian tumours were based on following features: 1. Bilateral lesion 2. Cystic mass 3. Evidence of solid areas 4. Cystic and solid masses 5. Evidence of metastasis. Data regarding histopathology of the tumour collected from department of OBGY. Ultrasound examination included size, shape, echogenicity of the ovarian lesion in sagittal and transverse planes, Wall thickness, locularity of the lesion and calcification. Histopathological follow up of all cases taken for correlating the ultrasonography.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis will be carried out with the help of SPSS (version 20) for Windows package (SPSS Science, Chicago, IL, USA).

Results

Table 1: Demographic data

Age groups in years	N	%
21-30	15	15
31-40	22	22
41-50	28	28
>51	35	35

In present study, most of the patients (35%) with ovarian tumour were in the age group 51 year old and above, followed by age group of 41-50 years (28%). Mean age of the patient was 45.35±3.4 years.

Table 2: Distribution of patients of ovarian tumour according to symptoms

Symptoms	N	%
Abdominal Pain	94	94
Abdominal Mass	65	65
Backache	32	32
Pressure Symptoms	20	20

In our study, most common symptom was abdominal pain 94 (94%) followed by abdominal mass 65 (65%). Backache was seen 32 (32%) patients. pressure symptoms were seen in 20 (20%) patients. Pressure symptoms included increased frequency of micturation, retention of urine and GI symptoms like constipation.

Table 3: Distribution of patients of ovarian tumour according to USG findings

USG Finding	Cases	Percentage
Cystic	32	32
Solid	30	30
Cystic+ Solid	34	34
Liver Metastasis	4	4
Total	100	100

Majority of the patients 34 (34%) were having cystic + solid consistency followed by cystic consistency 32 (32%). Solid consistency on ultrasonography was seen in 30 (30%). Liver metastasis was seen in 4 (4%) patients.

Table 4: Types of Tumours According to Ultrasonography Finding in patients with ovarian tumour

	Cystic	Solid	Cystic + Solid	Liver Metastasis	
Benign	32	24	14	-	70
Malignant	-	6	20	4	30

In present study, based on ultrasonography findings most of the benign ovarian tumours were having cystic consistency. Most of the malignant tumour was having both cystic and solid consistency. 4 patients with malignant ovarian tumour had liver metastasis. Association between tumour type and ultrasonography finding was found to be significant ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The pathology of ovarian tumour is one of the most complex areas of gynaecology, because the ovaries give rise to greater range and variety of tumours than does any other organ. A female's risk at birth of having ovarian tumour sometime in her life is 6-7%, of having ovarian cancer is almost 1.5% and dying from ovarian cancer is 1%. [12] A number of non neoplastic and neoplastic lesion occur within the ovaries. They can present from the neonatal age to post menopausal age. Most are functional in nature and fade away with minimal treatment. However, ovarian cyst can herald an underlying malignant process. When cyst are large, persistent, or painful, surgery may be required. [13,14] Benign ovarian cysts are the commonest constituting about 90% of ovarian tumours. Ovarian tumours are generally difficult to detect until they are of advanced stage or large in size. Ultrasonography is a relatively simple and non-invasive diagnostic method that provides clinicians with useful information relevant for determining the optimal management strategy for a given patient.

In present study, most of the patients (35%) with ovarian tumour were in the age group 51 year old and above, followed by age group of 41-50 years (28%). Mean age of the patient was 45.35 ± 3.4 years. Similarly Khurana and Satia found 50 mean age of the patients was 37 years. [15] In our study, most common symptom was abdominal pain 94 (94%)

followed by abdominal mass 65 (65%). Backache was seen 32 (32%) patients. pressure symptoms were seen in 20 (20%) patients. Pressure symptoms included increased frequency of micturation, retention of urine and GI symptoms like constipation. It is comparable to studies by Sumaira et al [16] (70.59%), Tarek Ramadan Abbas et al [17] (66.66%), Kanthikar et al [18] (29.33%).

Majority of the patients 34 (34%) were having cystic + solid consistency followed by cystic consistency 32 (32%). Solid consistency on ultrasonography was seen in 30 (30%). Liver metastasis was seen in 4 (4%) patients. Present study was comparable with Prabhakar et al [19] Mishra et al [20] and Kanthikar et al [18] where benign tumours were having cystic consistency while malignant tumours were cystic and solid.

In present study, based on ultrasonography findings most of the benign ovarian tumours were having cystic consistency. Most of the malignant tumour was having both cystic and solid consistency. 4 patients with malignant ovarian tumour had liver metastasis. Association between tumour type and ultrasonography finding was found to be significant ($p < 0.001$). benign ovarian tumors more often present in women of reproductive age group. Combination symptoms along with constitutional symptoms were present in all malignant patients which contradicts few other studies which report 7-15% of ovarian cancer patients are asymptomatic, when diagnosed. [21,22]

Conclusion

On ultrasonography benign ovarian tumours are having cystic consistency and malignant tumours were having cystic+ solid consistency.

References

1. Jain R, Patel P, Goyal S. Clinico-pathological study of ovarian tumors at tertiary care hospital, Udaipur. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2021 Feb 1;10(2):555-9.
2. Uday A. A study of ultrasonography findings in ovarian tumour at a tertiary health care centre. *MedPulse International Journal of Radiology*. June 2020; 14(3): 63-66
3. Pankaj S, Nazneen S, Choudhary V, Kumari J, Kumari A, Kumari A. Retrospective Observational Study of Surgically Treated Gynaecological Malignancies at a Tertiary Care Centre in Bihar. *Indian Journal of Gynecologic Oncology*. 2019 Mar;17:1-6.
4. Scully RE, Young RH, Clement PB. Tumors of the ovary, maldeveloped gonads, fallopian tube, and broad ligament. *American Registry of Pathology*; 1998.
5. Whittmore AS, Harris R, Itnyre J, Collaborative Ovarian Cancer Group. Characteristics relating to ovarian cancer risk: collaborative analysis of 12 US case-control studies: II. Invasive epithelial ovarian cancers in white women. *American journal of epidemiology*. 1992 Nov 15;136(10):1184-203.
6. Collaborative Group on Epidemiological Studies of Ovarian Cancer. Ovarian cancer and smoking: individual participant meta-analysis including 28 114 women with ovarian cancer from 51 epidemiological studies. *The Lancet Oncology*. 2012 Sep 1;13(9):946-56.
7. Fonseaa M. A clinic-histopathological review of ovarian masses at a tertiary care centre. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2018;7(10):4139-44.
8. Mohapatro M, Dash D, Rao ES. A study on clinicopathological spectrum of ovarian tumours in tertiary care centre. *J Evid Med Healthcare*. 2017;4(37):2223-30.
9. Timmerman D, Schwarzler P, Collins WP, Claerhout F, Coenen M, Amant F, et al... Subjective assessment of adnexal masses with the use of ultrasonography: an analysis of interobserver variability and experience. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol* 1999;13:11-16.
10. Valentin L. Prospective cross-validation of Doppler ultrasound examination and gray-scale ultrasound imaging for discrimination of benign and malignant pelvic masses. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol* 1999;14:273-283.
11. Valentin L. Pattern recognition of pelvic masses by grayscale ultrasound imaging: the contribution of Doppler ultrasound. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol* 1999;14:338-347.
12. Scully Robert E, Young Robert H, Clement Phillip B. Atlas of Tumor Pathology. Tumors of the ovary, maldeveloped gonads, fallopian tube and broad ligament. 3rd series, Fascicle 23. Armed Force Institute of Pathology, 1999.
13. Scully Robert E, Young Robert H, Clement Phillip B. Atlas of Tumor Pathology. Tumors of the ovary, maldeveloped gonads, fallopian tube and broad ligament. 3rd series, Fascicle 23. Armed Force Institute of Pathology, 1999.
14. Grimes DA, Jones LB, Lopez LM, Schulz KF. Oral contraceptives for functional ovarian cysts. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2011(9).
15. Holt VL, Cushing-Haugen KL, Daling JR. Risk of functional ovarian cyst: effects of smoking and marijuana use according to body mass index. *American journal of epidemiology*. 2005 Mar 15;161(6):520-5.
16. Khurana I, Satia MN. Preoperative evaluation of ovarian masses with color Doppler and its correlation with pathological finding. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2016 Jul 1;5(7):2084-93.
17. Sumaira Y, Aiman Y, Mohammad A. Clinicohistological pattern of ovarian tumours in Peshawar region.
18. Abbas TR, Matar ER. The incidence and histopathological patterns of ovarian tumours in bab Alshaaria University Hospitals: Retrospective study. *Nat science*. 2015;13(4): 37-41.
19. Kanthikar SN, Dravid NV, Deore PN, Nilkumbh DB, Suryawanshi KH. Clinico-Histopathological Analysis of Neoplastic And Non-Neoplastic Lesions of The Ovary: A 3-Years Prospective Study In Dhule, North Maharashtra, India. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2014 Aug; 8(8):4-7.
20. Prabhakar BR, Maingi K. Ovarian tumours--prevalence in Punjab. *Indian journal of pathology & microbiology*. 1989 Oct 1;32(4):276-81.
21. Misra RK, Sharma SP, Gupta U, Gaur R, Mishra SD. Pattern of ovarian neoplasm in eastern UP. *J Obstet Gynecol India*. 1991;30:242-46.
22. Terzic MM, Dotlic J, Likic I, Ladjovic N, Brndusic N, Arsenovic N, Maricic S, Mihailovic T, Andrijasevic S. Current diagnostic approach to patients with adnexal masses: which tools are relevant in routine praxis?. *Chinese Journal of Cancer Research*. 2013 Feb;25(1):55.
23. Wasim T, Majrroh A, Siddiq S. Comparison of clinical presentation of benign and malignant ovarian tumours. *J Pak Med Assoc*. 2009;59(1):18-21.